

Congresso de **Iniciação Científica**
da Universidade de Brasília e do Distrito Federal

Study of seismic anisotropy of the upper mantle with the division of SKS and SKKS shear waves in the North and Midwest regions of Brazil

Lyara Villanova Silverio, George Sand França, Cristobal Condori, Marco Gonzaga
Seismological Observatory - SIS, University of Brasilia - UnB

Abstract

The shear wave division method has been applied to study anisotropy in the upper mantle at some seismographic stations in the North and Midwest regions of Brazil, where it is used in order to understand the direction of the asthenospheric flow. The directional dependence on seismic wave propagation is strongly related to the preferential alignment (LPO) of olivine, a parameter that indicates geodynamic processes of mantle deformations associated with past and current regimes. The study area is composed of a tectonic structure that is dominated by the Amazonian Craton, one of the most expressive areas of the Archean-Proterozoic period, which still has little geophysical and geological knowledge. For the analysis, the SKS and SKKS phases of events occurred between 2014 and 2017 ($88^\circ < \Delta < 130^\circ$), with a magnitude equal to / greater than 5.5 Mw, were used, all detected in stations of the Brazilian Seismographic Network (RSBR-UnB). For measurements of the seismic anisotropy parameters, the fast polarization direction (Φ) and the delay time (δt) between the fast and slow polarization direction are determined, using three techniques: minimum energy, rotation-correlation and the eigenvalue. In this work, we found results where the fast polarization directions are oriented almost perpendicularly to Conrad's theoretical flow model in the Amazonian Craton region and approximately parallel to the absolute movement of the South American plate, and it is therefore proposed that anisotropy in these regions is related the concordance between geological and seismic evidence for the location of the Craton's edge.

Keywords: Anisotropy, Amazonian craton, shear waves.